

EFFECTS OF MATRIX VISCOELASTICITY ON INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF ACRYLIC/CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES

Tommaso Pini, Francesco Briatico-Vangosa, Roberto Frassine and Marta Rink

Department of Chemistry, Materials and Chemical Engineering, Politecnico di Milano
Piazza Leonardo da Vinci 32, 20133 Milano, Italy

Email: tommaso.pini@polimi.it, web page: <http://www.chem.polimi.it/polyenglab>

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ABSTRACT

The interlaminar fracture toughness of an acrylic resin/carbon fibre composite was studied in relation to the fracture toughness of the matrix. Composites were prepared by infusing the matrix monomers into the fibre stack and then letting the matrix to polymerize in-situ. The deformation rate and temperature dependence of both the plain matrix and the composite were analysed and by applying the time-temperature superposition the crack speed range was extended. The fracture toughness of the composite turned out to be higher than that of the plain matrix indicating that also other mechanisms linked to the presence of the fibres are present in the composite. The fracture toughness of the pure matrix increased with crack speed as it is expected for a viscoelastic material while the composite showed a constant value at varying crack speed. Further investigation is in due course to better analyse the damage mechanisms taking place in the composite during fracture.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic composites have met large interest due to their properties, such as recyclability, the possibility of being reprocessed and a short processing cycle [1]. Further, thermoplastic composites, usually show greater fracture toughness compared to thermosetting ones [2]. The main drawback in the use of thermoplastic matrices is their high melt viscosity which leads to a difficult impregnation of the fibres when adopting processing techniques already developed and widely used in the field of thermosets. To overcome this issue among the techniques suitable for thermoplastics [3-5] a possible technique, which was adopted in this research is infusion moulding, using in-situ polymerization [6].

The relationship between matrix and composite toughness was widely investigated and reviewed by Bradley [7]. The interlaminar fracture toughness of the composite generally turns out to be higher than that of the plain matrix due to different reasons: the fracture surface is more corrugated and hence more extended in the case of the composite than in the case of plain resin; moreover, the fibres themselves introduce additional dissipative mechanisms such as fibre bridging behind the crack tip, fibre pull-out and fibre breakage. In some cases, the toughness of the composite may result lower than that of the plain matrix: the presence of the fibres can act as a physical constraint to the development of the plastic zone ahead the crack tip, not allowing the full exploitation of the matrix toughness in the composite. As long as the plastic zone is smaller than the resin-rich region between two adjacent plies the fracture toughness of the resin is fully transferred to the composite, which is not necessarily the case for larger plastic zones.

In this research the interlaminar fracture toughness of a thermoplastic acrylic based composite was studied in relation to the toughness of the relevant plain matrix applying the fracture mechanics approach [8-9]. The effect of the viscoelastic behaviour of the matrix on the composite was analysed by comparing the trend of the strain energy release rate, G_{IC} , as a function of crack speed for both the matrix and the composite.

2 MATERIALS

Two thermoplastic acrylic resins developed by Arkema company were considered: plain and rubber-toughened.

Neat resin samples were prepared by pouring the monomer/initiator solution between two sealed aluminium plates, and allowing the polymerization reaction to take place at room temperature for the plain resin and at 80°C for the toughened resin. A thermal treatment at 120°C was applied to ensure a complete conversion.

Composite samples were prepared by infusion molding using the plain resin only and unidirectional T700 12 K carbon fibres with a sizing compatible with vinylester/polyester, obtaining composites with a volume fibre fraction of roughly 60%. A thin film (15 µm) of polyimide was inserted in the mid-plane of fibre stack in order to produce an initial delamination on one side. The same thermal treatment as in the case of the neat resin was applied.

3 TESTING

The following test methods were adopted:

3.1 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA)

DMA was performed to study the small strain viscoelastic behaviour of the plain resin. Isothermal tests, in three-point bending test configuration, were performed at 8 temperatures between 26 and 96 °C at 20 different frequencies between 0.1 and 10 Hz. By applying the time temperature equivalence, a master curve of the storage modulus, E' , and the relevant shift factors were obtained.

3.2 Single Edge Notched Bending (SENB)

Neat resin fracture toughness, G_{IC} , was evaluated according to ISO 13586 standard, in which a prismatic notched specimen is tested in a three-point bending test configuration (Figure 1). Specimens with dimensions of 70x15x4.5 mm were adopted and notches with a tip radius less than 10 µm, were introduced by chisel-wise cutting with a razor blade.

The tests were performed at different displacement rates (0.1, 1 and 10 mm/min) and three different temperatures (23, 40 and 60 °C).

Figure 1: SENB configuration.

Critical strain energy release rate was obtained from the following equation:

$$G_{IC} = \frac{U}{h \cdot w \cdot \varphi\left(\frac{a}{w}\right)} \quad (1)$$

in which U is the energy at crack growth onset evaluated from load-displacement curve, h and w are specimen thickness and width respectively, and φ is the energy calibration factor which depends on the ratio between the initial crack length a and the width.

Tests were videorecorded and synchronized with load/displacement data in order to allow for

simultaneous load, displacement and crack length recording at any time during the test.

3.3 Double Cantilever Beam (DCB)

Composite interlaminar fracture toughness was evaluated accordingly to ISO 15024; prismatic (250x20x3 mm) specimens with the longitudinal axis parallel to the fibres were adopted. Load blocks were attached to the specimens at the end where the initial delamination was present (Figure 2).

The tests were performed at different displacement rates (0.2, 2 and 20 mm/min) and three different temperatures (23, 40 and 60 °C).

Figure 2: DCB configuration.

Fracture toughness G_{IC} was evaluated as follows:

$$G_{IC} = \frac{3P\delta}{2b(a+|\Delta|)} \cdot \frac{F}{N} \quad (2)$$

in which P and δ are the load and the displacement respectively, b is the specimen width, a is the crack length, Δ is a correcting factor taking into account that the beam arms are not perfectly built-in and F and N are the correcting factors for large displacements and use of load blocks respectively.

For both fracture tests crack propagation speed was evaluated from the video-recordings and fracture toughness values were plotted as a function of crack speed with the same synchronizing procedure described previously.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 DMA

Figure 3(a) reports the storage modulus, E' , as a function of the frequency for the different testing temperatures. The curves at the different temperatures were superimposed by a horizontal shift factor and a master curve, also shown in Figure 3(a), was obtained. Shift factors are reported in Figure 3(b) as a function of temperature.

Figure 3: Plain resin storage modulus master curve referred to 26 °C (a) and relevant shift factors (b).

4.2 Fracture

For the plain resin, a brittle fracture behaviour is observed. Values of G_{IC} at crack initiation for the plain resin are plotted in Figure 4 as a function of the crack speed just after the crack onset for the three temperatures.

For the composite, a combination of stable and stick-slip propagation was observed. By plotting the crack length, a , as a function of time, considering both stable and stick-slip propagation, a fairly constant value of crack speed was observed during each single test. The values of G_{IC} of the composite as a function of this crack speed at the different temperatures are also shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: G_{IC} vs. crack speed plain resin (squares) and the composite (triangles) at different testing temperatures.

Following the approach of [10,11] the shift factors found from DMA were applied in order to obtain fracture toughness master curves (Figure 5).

Figure 5: G_{IC} vs. reduced crack speed for the plain resin (squares) and the composite (triangles).

Figure 5 shows that the fracture toughness of the composite material is higher than that of the plain resin; this result was expected due to additional dissipative deformation mechanisms related to the presence of the fibres taking place in the composite. The identification of these mechanisms is still under investigation. It is to be noticed that some plastic deformation took place in the DCB specimen arms, especially at the higher temperature, and therefore further experiments with thicker specimens will be performed.

The plain matrix shows an increasing trend of fracture toughness as a function of crack speed. The composite showed a fairly constant value and this finding and its possible interpretation needs further experimental work. Further expansion of crack speed range using different specimens, SEM analysis of the fracture surfaces and plain resin yielding characterization are actually being performed.

Some fracture tests were performed on the toughened resin at room temperature, the results are shown in Figure 6 together to those of the plain resin. The fracture toughness is as expected much higher and the trend with crack speed is similar to that of the plain resin. This second matrix seems promising and preparation and testing of the relevant composites are in progress.

Figure 6: G_{IC} vs. reduced crack speed for the plain and the toughened acrylic resin.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A new carbon fibre composite having an acrylic thermoplastic matrix obtained by in-situ polymerization was prepared. Its fracture toughness is much higher than that of the plain matrix. Further testing is on going to identify the dissipative deformation mechanisms active in the composite at the different temperatures and deformation rates.

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